

INNOVATION METHODS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article talks about the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in the methodology of foreign language teaching and their use.

Key words: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competence, didactics.

Today's educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. He studied the classification of the participants of the innovation process, their attitude to the innovation, and others. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific directions. "Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that had an impact on our country. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. As a result of this, the President's naming of this year as the "Year of Youth Support and Public Health" has increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be wrong to say that the wide application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the fields of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, among the public or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time when international relations are on the rise. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of relatives and neighbors who are representatives of other nations.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages largely depends on the theoretical development of foreign language teaching methodology issues and the creative application of theory in practice.

The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics - what do we teach? is the content of education. Methodology - how do we teach? means educational methods and methods. Method - the concept of methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and means the means of ways and methods leading to a certain goal. In various literature, the narrow and broad meaning of the term can be found. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense means the concept related to the concrete lesson process of education. It is interpreted as a controlled teaching process that includes instructions related to the planning of lessons and the preparation of teaching materials. The term "method" broadly refers to the selection, classification and distribution of teaching materials. "Didactics" and "methodology" have been used in the narrow sense in the Federal Republic of Germany since the 1960s. Accordingly, what is the content of didactic education taught? How are teaching methods taught? He deals with his issues. Learning foreign languages is not only a means of intellectual education, but also a process of personality formation by getting to know the educational resources and values of a foreign culture and applying them to one's own cultural life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools have been seen as educating the privileged few.

The method of teaching a foreign language means the set of activities of the teacher and the student that ensures the achievement of the practical, general

educational, educational and developmental goals of teaching a foreign language. The term "method" is used in the sense of "set of educational methods" and "direction of education". First, in the theory of education, the process is used in the sense of methods, and in the second sense, we can find it in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, translation method, correct method, conscious-comparative method, traditional method, intensive method, etc. are considered as foreign language teaching methods.

Method without translation. Different forms of this method are known historically. They can be divided into two large groups: natural and correct methods. Learning a foreign language in a natural way should be similar to the conditions of mastering the mother tongue. The main goal of the method is to create an opportunity to learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language. The most important of the principles included in the natural method is to create a language environment. Various approaches have appeared in the practical application of the advanced methodical principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative activity of the method exponents.

The new interpretation of the goal of foreign language education was mainly based on the results of pragmatic linguistics research. This field of linguistics interprets language as a field of human activity rather than a system of linguistic forms. A set of new conclusions, which began to be collected in the field of foreign language education since the beginning of the 70s, led to intense discussions in the field of setting educational goals. New curricula were adopted, which define the main directions of foreign language education, with the goal of "teaching students to communicate", "Befaeigung zur Kommunikation" (communicative Kompetenz). In the 70s, the "communicative method" was proven in several stages after a series of attempts. In this way, the science of methodology was developing. We cannot master any foreign language without studying its methodology in depth. The method of "communicative didactics" is also considered important in the methodology of foreign language teaching. Communicative didactics includes the following

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted teaching, and in this process a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing a foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in

the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. Since the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics is created.

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